

IATEFL 2016 BIRMINGHAM CONFERENCE SELECTIONS - BOOK REVIEW

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In this article, I would like to summarize the conference book, entitled '**IATEFL 2016 Birmingham Conference Selections**'. The abbreviation IATEFL stands for the International Association of Teachers of English As a Foreign Language. The editorial committee members of this conference book are **Edward de Chazal, Chris Lima and Amos Paran**. It was edited by **Tania Pattison**. It was first published in 2017 in the United Kingdom. The printed International Standard Book Number of this book is 978-1-901095-89-0 and the digital International Standard Book Number of this book is 978-1-901095-91-3.

The book starts with the editor's introduction. As it has been mentioned by Pattison (2017: p.8) that;

"The 50th Annual International Conference attracted a record 3,100 delegates from 111 countries and there was plenty for them to enjoy. Three of the plenary speakers took the opportunity to look back over the last fifty years. Diane Larsen-Freeman explored metaphors related to ELT, from computer input to ecological affordances; Scott Thornbury gave us a review of teaching methodology since the 1960s; and David Crystal discussed changes in the English language that have taken place since the first conference, when delegates might have worn 'winklepickers' and Talked on their 'triphones'. Silvana Richardson brought us right up to date with a much-discussed plenary talk on the status of non-native English-speaking teachers- surely an issue to pay attention to as we move forward. Storyteller Jan Blake was as entertaining as ever at the closing plenary."

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This conference book has 12 chapters. The title of the first chapter is '**Ready to Learn: Psychological Aspects of Learning**'. The sub-titles of the first chapter are the following:

- 1.1. Plenary: Shifting metaphors: from computer input to ecological affordances to adaptation *Diane Larsen-Freeman*
- 1.2. Exploring psychology in language learning and teaching *Sarah Mercer*
- 1.3. The joys of second language learning: a positive psychology framework: *Siân Ethrington*
- 1.4. Learnernance: towards a new relationship to teaching-learning *Stephen Scott Brewer*
- 1.5. Teachers' views on motivation in relation to their motivational practice *Mariia Prykhodchenko*
- 1.6. Language learner autonomy: teachers' perceptions and practices *Kasim koruyun and Nazife Aydinoglu*
- 1.7. Zen zone: meditation in the EFL Classroom *Monique Simson*.

In this chapter, the plenary speaker Diana Larsen-Freeman talks about the metaphors such as a computer metaphor and an ecological metaphor. Larsen-Freeman (2017:10-11) states that;

"Fifty years ago, research into the relatively new field of investigation which later became known as SLA (Second Language Acquisition) was just underway. Many scholars mark its founding (at almost exactly the same time as IATEFL) in 1967 with the publication of Edinburgh University professor S. Pit Corder's article 'The significance of learner's errors.' In the article, Corder maintained that many learner errors could not be simply attributed to interference from the learners' native languages. There was evidence of L1 influence to be sure, but there were also errors that indicated that learners were making incorrect inferences about the rules of the new language they were learning. In other words, the learners were more cognitively engaged than they had previously been given credit for. It is important to understand that, at the time Corder's claim was exciting. It reflected a break with dominant behaviourist thinking and instead linked SLA to the cognitive revolution that was occurring in a number of related fields, especially linguistics and psychology.

Other SLA research attested to the systematic nature of the learners' language, suggesting the existence of universal sequences of development and acquisition orders."

It has also been stated by Larsen-Freeman (2017:11) that;

"It is also the case that metaphors are a product of the zeitgeist. It is not surprising, then that at the time of the cognitive revolution in the middle of the last century; computer input/output metaphors were prevalent. Similarly, it is perfectly understandable that

with today's consciousness concerning the environment, a computer metaphor might give way to an ecological one. It is also the case that any metaphor today would reflect our feeling of being interconnected with others, a feeling which has been heightened through movement of populations, technological innovations, the interdependence of national economies and the increasingly transnational lives that many are leading".

The title of the second chapter of this conference book is '**Approaches to Teacher Education**'. Peter Grundy and Penny Ur outline their ideas on teacher training in this chapter. The sub-titles of this chapter are as follows: **2.1.** ELT Journal/ IATEFL Debate: Teacher training is a waste of time by *Peter Grundy and Penny Ur* **2.2.** Promoting creativity through teacher training by *Daniel Xerri* **2.3.** Changing the way we approach learning styles in teacher education by *Carol Lethaby and Patricia Harries* **2.4.** Rethinking reflection on the intensive TEFL Course by *Daniel Baines* **2.5.** Personal Learning from the CELTA: An auto-ethnography approach by *Bethany Miall* **2.6.** The Horby Scholars' panel presentation: Teaching practice: some local perspectives on a global practice Convenor: *Martin Wedell, with the A.S. Hornby Scholars* at IATEFL 2016 **2.7.** Experiments with e-portfolios for teacher training and development by *Marcela Cintra* **2.8.** Instilling a passion for research in pre-service teachers by *Elena Onchevska Ager* **2.9.** Teacher educators' voices on undergraduate TEFL Curriculum innovation in Chile by *Loreto Aliaga-Salas* **2.10.** Signature Event: The Teacher Trainer Journal 30th birthday panel by *Tessa Woodward, Varinder Unlu, Briony Beaven and Seth Lindstromberg*.

The title of the third chapter of this conference book is '**The Big Picture: Issues in ELT Methodology**'. This chapter is about the ELT classrooms and some of the essential issues on methods in ELT.

In this chapter, Thornbury (2017: 56) states that;

"On the occasion of both IATEFL's and TESOL's 50th anniversaries, it is instructive to look back at the period during which both organisations were founded (in 1966 and 1967 respectively), and take stock of what has changed since then, and-more tellingly, perhaps-what has not.

In 1966 alone, a number of key events seemed to presage a major shift in thinking that, with hindsight, we recognise as the first intimations of the advent of communicative language teaching (CLT)."

It has also been stated by Thornbury (2017:59) that;

“To summarize, then both TESOL and IATEFL emerged at a time when two educational discourses (labelled, for convenience, A and B) were competing to occupy the rapidly expanding domain of English language teaching. These competing discourses were diametrically opposed across a number of dimensions, according to the position they adopted with regard to theories both of language and of learning, and to instructional goals, syllabus organisation and instructional processes and sequences. These dimensions are summarised in Table 3.1.1.”

	Discourse A	Discourse B
theory of Language	structural	functional
theory of Learning	habit formation	socially constructed
instructional goals	native-like accuracy	communicative competence
syllabus organisation	atomistic/synthetic (grammatical structures)	holistic/analytic (functions; tasks)
instructional processes	interventionist; transmissive	non-interventionist; dialogic
instructional sequence	accuracy first: present-practice-produce [PPP]	fluency first: task-based instruction

Table 3.1.1: Competing educational discourses in the 1960s

The sub-titles of this chapter are the following: **3.1.** Plenary: 1966 and all that: A Critical History of ELT by *Scott Thornbury* **3.2.** Airdrop your students: Immersion learning principles in the classroom by Tony Penston **3.3.** Using Learners’ Own Language in Teaching English: Revisioning the L1-L2 Relationship by John *Simpson* **3.4.** Accelerating Input and Exposure In the English Language Classroom by *Mike Bilbrough* **3.5.** Gamification for language learning by Wade P. *Alley and Enrique Barba* **3.6.** Game-inspired course design: creating opportunity for agency **3.7.** Moving Beyond Technology In the Classroom by Rhoda McGraw **3.8.** ELT Conversation: ELT as an industry by *Philip Kerr*.

The title of the fourth chapter is ‘**Working Towards Inclusivity in ELT**’. This chapter is related with the teachers and learners who may be marginalised within ELT and explores ways in ELT classes. The sub-titles of this chapter are the following: **4.1.** Plenary: The ‘native factor’: the haves and the have-nots... And why we still need to talk about this in 2016 by *Silvana Richardson* **4.2.** I’m a non-native English speaker teacher-hear me roar by *Dita Philips* **4.3.** National Geographic Learning Signature Event: What does it mean to be a global citizen? by *Hugh Dellar, Hetain Patel, Gavin McLean, Gilian Davidson* **4.4.** Prejudiced against your own students? Teachers’ unconscious bias by *Ali H. Al-Hoorie* **4.5.** Supporting Learners with English As an Additional Language in London Schools by *Jill Coleman* **4.6.** Covert syllabuses **4.7.** Too PC for ELT? The

invisibility of non-sexist language in coursebooks by *Jemma Prior* 4.8. How to spot dyslexia: A field guide for teachers 4.9. Visual Learning Tools for Students With Dyslexia by *Julia Koifman* 4.10. Deaf-blind to inclusion? Adapting examinations fairly for disabled candidates by *Diana Metzner*

The title of the fifth chapter is '**Working (and playing) with Words**'. This chapter focuses on the lexical issues in ELT. It starts with David Crystal's report of his plenary talk on the lexical, grammatical and phonological changes in ELT in the last 50 years. The sub-titles of this chapter are as follows: 5.1. Plenary: Who would of thought it? The English Language 1966-2066 by David *Crystal* 5.2. Vocabulary Learning Practices and Vocabulary Learning Outcomes: Match or Mismatch? by *Mario López-Barrios* 5.3. The Academic World List: Teachers' Practice, Attitudes and Beliefs by *Chris Banister* 5.4. Students' use of wordlists and its impact on written assessment by *Neslihan Erbil* 5.5. Teacher-driven corpus development: The online restaurant review by *Chad Langford and Joshua Albair* 5.6. Creative Vocabulary: Playing with words by *Charlie Hadfield* 5.7. Dada machine, or (re) imagining activities for the classroom by *Roy Bicknell*.

The title of the sixth chapter is '**From Critical Thinking to Academic Writing**'. This chapter is about the topics on English for Academic Purposes. The sub-titles of this chapter are the following: 6.1. The Language of Critical Thinking by *Edward de Chazal* 6.2. Ways of engaging learners in critical thinking at the university level by *Zeynep İskenderoğlu Önel* 6.3. Teaching Caterpillars to Fly: Nurturing EFL Students' Learning Through Inquiry by *Blerta Mustafa* 6.4. Undergraduate Collaborative Essays: Constructive, Not a Cop-out by *Peter Levrai and Averil Bolster* 6.5. Paraphrasing: Improving Skills and Attitudes in ESL Students by *Alexander M. Lewko* 6.6. How to Optimise EAP Tutorial Time: Introducing the 20-minute structured format by *David Jay* 6.7. Building Better Turkish 11 English Academic Writers by *David Reed Albachten* 6.8. Stimulus Materials for Teacher-Writers In the Classroom by *Stephanie Xerri Agius*.

The title of the seventh chapter of the conference book is '**From Listening to Speaking**'. In this chapter, the writers focused on listening and speaking, including pronunciation. The sub-titles of this chapter are the following: 7.1. Using transcription to improve noticing and develop effective learning plans by *Robert J. Werner*. 7.2. Teacher Awareness of Classroom Conversation Analysis: Pedagogy and Practice 7.3. 'It Doesn't Reflect My Identity': Learner Reactions to 'Natural' English by *Carol Griffiths and Adem Sonuç* 7.4. Teaching Discussion In Academic Settings Using Genre-based Methodology by *Anna Makarova* 7.5. Scaffolding the Development of Academic Speaking Skills Online by *Vasikili Celia Antoniou* 7.6. Teaching Pronunciation Using the Prosody Pyramid: Simplicity is the Key by *Judy B. Gilbert* 7.7. They Don't Do Scottish Accents by

Robin Walker 7.8. Designing bespoke EAP listening and speaking materials by *Lesley Kendall*

The title of the eighth chapter of this conference book is '**English for Specific (Academic) Purposes**'. This short chapter is about the papers which are related with the subjects on English for specific academic purposes and vocational purposes in various parts of the world. The sub-titles of this chapter are as follows: **8.1.** ESP Teacher Education: An Online, in-service, ESP Teacher Training Course by *Elis Kakaoulli* **8.2.** An English Quality Strategy for Vocational Education in Saudi Arabia by *Paul Woods and Waleed Bajouda* **8.3.** Motivating Media Students With Ten-Second Self-Produced social Media Videos by *Diane Nancy Brown* **8.4.** English for Library Staff: Creation of An ESP Course by *Caroline Hyde-Simon* **8.5.** An Online EAP Collaboration for Science Graduates by *Anna Rolinska and William Guariento*.

In the eighth chapter, Constantinou and Papadima-Sophocleous (2017:161) indicate that;

"The findings carry important implications for the design and implementation of the ESP Teacher training programme that this study aspires to propose. Some of the most important are the following:

- 1. Literature shows an intense need for ESP teacher training worldwide. Moreover, it presents useful findings that could constitute a basis for future ESP teacher training programmes. This short report can only refer briefly to some general aspects of the findings, but according to the literature, any ESP teacher training programme should be governed by the principles of ESP and the multifaceted role of the ESP practitioner. Moreover, it should be built on the idea that the ESP learning process should be the result of collaboration and cooperation between the ESP practitioner, content teachers, professionals, students and other ESP educators. Finally, ESP teacher training should be based on the idea of continuing Professional development and life-long learning.*
- 2. The needs analysis survey reveals useful findings related to the ESP teacher training programme that the present study will propose upon its completion. First of all, the profiles of the ESP higher and vocational education practitioners in Cyprus and Greece are identified, as well as the aspects of their ESP teaching practices that need improvement. Furthermore, conclusions can be drawn preferable modes of teaching, as well as regarding components that ESP practitioners would like to be in an ESP teacher training course. Finally, the survey illustrates that most of the practitioners*

consider ESP teacher training to be useful and that they would be willing to participate in such training."

The title of the ninth chapter is '**Working With Young Learners**'. This chapter is related with the topics on teaching English to children and teenagers in the world. The sub-titles of this chapter are as follows: **9.1.** Real Books to Picturebooks: 30 years of Illustrated Literature in ELT by *Sandie Mourão, Gail Ellis, Janice Bland, Smiljana Narančić Kovać* and *Opal Dunn*. **9.2.** Six strategies for six year olds: Teaching English to Young Learners by *Samuel Lefever* **9.3.** Top Tips for Teaching Teens by *Sophie Handy* **9.4.** 'Englishphobia' among secondary school students: Symptoms, Diagnosis and Treatment by *Mercedes Agueda Foligna* **9.5.** Task-based tests for diagnostic purposes: A school- network-initiated Project by *Sandra Lucietto* **9.6.** Embracing Students' Digital Literacies in our teaching Jodi Wainwright **9.7.** Supporting Teachers in Using Technology for ELT in school systems by *Radhika Gholkar* **9.8.** My health! My environment! Project work with teenagers by *Lindsey Clark* **9.9.** Multimodal Reviewing Activities: Children Talking About Their English Learning by *Nayr Ibrahim* **9.10.** Teaching English At a Public School in Rio de Janeiro by *Patricia Santos*

In the ninth chapter, Mourão (2017:172) states that;

"A picturebook usually contains 32 pages and so, in many cases, the illustrations overflow into the other parts of the picturebook-the front and back covers, the endpapers, the copyright and dedication pages and the title page. When looking at picturebooks children respond to the whole picturebook, the pictures, the words and its design."

In the same chapter, it has been mentioned by Ellis (2017:172):

"Picturebooks provide a rich and motivating resource to develop basic vocabulary and phrases related to the content of a story, but they can also be used to develop multiliteracies. These include visual, emotional, cultural, nature, digital and moving image literacy; they also include learning literacy defined as an ethos, a culture and a way of life which involves 'being ready to develop our own learning capacities, develop the behaviours we now need as individual, including being willing to learn continuously, as competencies essential to thriving in a globally connected, digitally driven world'. (Wynn 2016)."

In the ninth chapter, Bland (2017:173) states that;

“The pictures in children’s literature frequently provide convincing access to cultural details and involve the affective dimension—they are physically present and frozen in time—strongly drawing the reader/beholder into the story-world. The pictures may transform into mental images that remain in the reader’s repertoire of experience, anchoring ideas, concepts and feelings along with language. Picturebooks reflecting cultural diversity move readers towards flexibility of perspective, away from the rather monolithic and often stereotyped input on other cultures provided in school textbooks. This is the meaning of intercultural competence, a competence that is designed to build bridges.”

As it has been denoted by Dunn (2017:174-175):

“Picturebooks are an excellent English experience for parents who want to use English at home in enjoyable ways. This is motivating for children as it shows parents are interested in their English learning experience. In this session, ten tips were shared to promote positive parent participation with picturebooks. These are as follows:

- 1. Inform parents how children learn a language, how you are going to teach it and the relevance of their support. Share your aims and objectives and include information about picturebooks you will use.*
- 2. Provide a list of picturebooks for parents to read at home and criteria for selecting picturebooks, e.g. consider books for boys.*
- 3. Set up a book borrowing classroom library system.*
- 4. Provide tips for reading and sharing English picturebooks (see Dunn2010).*
- 5. Suggest how to re-use home language teaching strategies when sharing English picturebooks, e.g. stressing important words, speaking slowly and giving generous encouragement.*
- 6. Suggest when to use the home language e.g. rephrasing children’s comments from L1 to L2; requesting short summaries of the story in the L1.*
- 7. Provide ideas for picturebook follow-up tasks.*
- 8. Explain any picturebook take-home activities clearly, so parents and child can complete these successfully.*
- 9. Provide regular information on progress in emails, class blogs and closed Facebook groups by featuring favourite picturebooks, related projects and photos of children’s work.*
- 10. Be sensitive to the individual needs and preferences of parents.*

Teachers can encourage parents, even with little spoken English, to playfully mediate English picturebooks, thus ensuring the learning triangle succeeds, for through English

picturebooks it is possible for enjoyable English experiences to be extended into the home."

The title of the tenth chapter is '**Learning Through Literature and the Arts**'. In this chapter, how art can be used to create successful lessons is explained. The contributions of the poetry, drama and painting in the ESL classes are handled. The sub-titles of this chapter are as follows: **10.1.** Contemporary poems in ELT: After-text Exercises and Activities by *Kirill Ignatov* **10.2.** Improving Speaking Skills in English Through Drama Activities by *Geeta Goyal* **10.3.** Drama As Global Text techniques for EAP Classes by *Stella Smyth* **10.4.** Moving Stories: Narrative and Video in ELT by *Kieran Donaghy* **10.5.** Let's Start With the Video by *Anna Whitcher* **10.6.** Motivating Students Into Creative Writing Through Art and Literature by *Maria Barberi*

The title of the eleventh chapter is '**Innovative Uses of Technology**'. This chapter is about teaching with technology and it is related with blended learning to collaborative writing and mobile technology in teaching English.

As Hockly (2017: 205-206) states that;

"Drawing on current research, my talk ended with what I consider to be some of the key ingredients of a successful blended approach:

Interaction: *There needs to be provision for interaction with other students, the teacher and possibly individuals in the wider world via the Internet.*

SLA Principles: *The blend needs to cater to the 12 SLA Principles described by Thornbury.*

Task Design and Tools: *Task design and the choice of tool (s) need to match.*

Materials: *Rather than only providing content, tasks and materials can also facilitate process (Mishan in McCarthy 2016).*

Integration of f2f and online: *There needs to be a clear link between f2f and online components of the course, with each complementing, supporting and developing the other.*

Evaluation: *Online work (Including speaking, if included in the blend) needs to be integrated into overall student evaluation.*

Context: *The blend needs to take into account the local context, including the skills, expectations and beliefs of both students and teachers.*

Teacher training: *Training is key for the successful implementation of blended approaches; to ensure that teachers understand the underlying principles, particularly of approaches like the flipped classroom, and are able to implement them effectively*

***Learner training:** Some learners find working autonomously a challenge, so your blend may require some learner training."*

In this chapter, the benefits of having a class that have been listed as follows by Robb (2017: 218):

1. *It is student-centred, interactive and communicative.*
2. *It creates dialogue amongst students and nurtures a social atmosphere.*
3. *It increases motivation and shifts the motivation from extrinsic to intrinsic.*
4. *It encourages sharing and extends learning.*
5. *It creates as personalized learning platform that students can refer to both inside and outside the classroom.*

The sub-titles of this chapter are **11.1.** Shaken Not Stirred: Blended Learning for Connoisseurs by *Nicky Hockly* **11.2.** iPad in the EFL Classroom: Perceptions and Practices by *Valentina Morgana* **11.3.** Mobile Learning and Wikis to Enhance Writing Skills by *Ruby Vurdien* **11.4.** Using Online Dialogue to Co-Construct Texts With Students by *Guy Meredith* **11.5.** Not just the Writing On the Wall by *Amadeu Marin* **11.6.** Can Learners Learn Alone With Only A Phone? Experiences With Mobile Learning In The Palestinian Territories by *Andrew Foster* **11.7.** Instant Messaging With Learners: Creepy Treehouse or Chilled-out Chatroom? by *Kat Robb* **11.8.** What Do Your Learners Think? Let Their Smartphones Tell You by *Tilly Harrison*.

The title of the twelfth chapter is '**Initiatives in Teacher Development**'. This is the final chapter of this conference book. The sub-titles of this chapter are **12.1.** PEP Talks for Teacher Development by *Nick Bilbrough* **12.2.** Mentoring Effectiveness In the Eyes of Mentors and Mentees by *Afaf Mishriki* and *Amani Demian* **12.3.** Blended Professional Development to Support Inexperienced Teachers by *Phil Bird* and *Celine Castelino* **12.4.** Addressing Quality Assurance and Professional Development for Online Teachers by *Kirsteen Donaghy* **12.5.** Bumpy ride or smooth transition? Moving from CELTA to EAP by *Andrew Preshous* **12.6.** How to Start Writing for Publication: A Teacher's Personal Journey by *Nergiz Kern* **12.7.** Exploring in-house Video Training Materials for 'Reflective' Teacher Development by *Teti Dragas* **12.8.** Using metaphors: Rethinking 'Thinking' in Reflective Practice by *Leslie Turpin* **12.9.** A Framework to Increase Teachers' Autonomy in Professional Development by *Daniella Seong Hui You*.

As a result, it can be said that this conference book is related with all levels of English language teaching classes and it is also related with many different kinds of skills in foreign language education. Anyone who is interested in foreign language education can get benefits from this book. As the private e-mail addresses are written

behind the articles of this conference book, questions related with the articles or professional development in English language teaching can be asked. As the articles of this conference book are not long, readers can finish reading this book in a very short time. Besides, readers will enjoy reading these articles as there are many different topics they can start to learn. Besides, I am sure this conference book will encourage many new teachers, instructors or experienced teachers or instructors to write more papers and to attend more international conferences on their professions. Instructors who have always written papers on the same subjects can easily find different topics after reading this book to develop their skills on English language teaching. I hope this book will be very useful for teaching many different skills in many different countries of the world.

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